

Intro to June 2024 Status of the Multi-fold Theory

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Abstract:

This report compiles the multi-fold theory papers available on the Multi-fold theory web site, as of June 22, 2024. This includes papers still to be published. It also includes subsequent comments ad discussions of related news and papers captured on the web site.

1. Introduction

This report compiles in one common place all the multi-fold theory papers available on the Multi-fold theory web site [8], as of June 22, 2024.

The latest papers have not yet been published outside the web site [8]. Their publications are future. Draft PDF pre-preprints can be requested from the author.

It also includes subsequent comments ad discussions of related news and papers captured on the web site, providing them as material that can be easily referenced or consulted. Some of these comments present new contributions, and can be of interest of their own. Other discuss other papers or update the readers about related papers.

A previous version till mid 2023 was published as [131].

We apologize in advance that this is just the result of spidering the web site [8] instead of a review paper or a real book compiling papers. This is for the future.

2. Overview of the multi-fold Theory

In a multi-fold universe [1,8-10,22], gravity emerges from entanglement through the multi-fold mechanisms. As a result, gravity-like effects appear in between entangled particles [1,24,25], whether they be real or virtual. Long range, massless gravity results from entanglement of massless virtual particles [1,26]. Entanglement of massive virtual particles leads to massive gravity contributions at very small scales [1,27]. It is at the base of the E/G Conjecture [24], and the main characteristics of the multi-fold theory [22]. Multi-folds mechanisms also result in a spacetime that is discrete, with a random walk fractal structure and non-commutative geometry [65], in a range of

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spatial scales, that is Lorentz invariant and where spacetime nodes and particles can be modeled with microscopic black holes [1,4]. All these recover General Relativity (GR) at large scales, and semi-classical model remain valid till smaller scale than usually expected. Gravity can therefore be added to the Standard Model (SM) resulting into what we define as SMG: the SM with gravity effects non-negligible at its scales. It can contribute to resolving several open issues with the Standard Model, and the standard cosmological model, without new Physics other than gravity [1,4-150]. These considerations hint at an even stronger relationship between gravity and the Standard Model, as finally shown in [23].

Among the multi-fold SMG discoveries, the apparition of an-always in-flight, and hence non-interacting, right-handed neutrinos, coupled to the Higgs boson, generated by chirality flips by gravity of the massless Weyl fermions, induced by 7D space time matter induction and scattering models, and hidden behind the Higgs boson or field at the entry points and exit points of the multi-folds. Massless Higgs bosons can be modeled as minimal microscopic black holes mark concretized spacetime locations. . They can condensate into Dirac Kerr-Newman soliton Qballs to produce massive and charged particles below the energy scales of the multi-fold electroweak symmetry breaking [1,4], and as random walk patterns above these scales [1,29,36,37] thereby providing a microscopic explanation for a the multi-fold kinematics and dynamics and associated unconstrained Kaluza Klein mechanisms [23,33,34,52,63,64,113,139], Higgs driven inflation [1,27], the electroweak symmetry breaking, the Higgs mechanism, the mass acquisition [139], and the chirality of fermions (and spacetime); all resulting from the multi-fold gravity electroweak symmetry breaking. The multi-fold theory has concrete implications on New Physics like supersymmetry, superstrings, M-theory and Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) [1,8-21,66,90,112,134].

Multi-folds are encountered in GR at Planck scales [5,6] and in Quantum Mechanics² (QM) if different suitable quantum reference frames (QRFs) are to be equivalent relatively to entangled, coherent or correlated systems [7]. This shows that GR and QM are different facets of something that they cannot well model: multi-folds [1,52,94,104].

3. Notable Additions Since [131]

Since [131], we can call out the following key new contributions (more at [8] and in this compilation):

- Update to [1], around EPR in [136,137].
- Detailed justifications of the multi-fold mechanisms in [140].
- Arguments in favor of the absence of systematic decoherence due to black holes [133].
- Proof and arguments for no supersymmetry (not specific to multi-fold universe), including a proof that the cosmological constant (even if time variable) is strictly positive and small in [112].
- Proof that gravity is quantum in [146].
- Discussions of spin, multi-fold spin, non-commutative spacetime, zitterbewegung, fermions, bosons and a new proof of the spin statistic theorem in the published update of [150].
- Related topics of interest: information and mass [145], challenges with warp drives [129] and the Minkowski – Abraham dilemma holds [132].

Meanwhile [151], published on [8], but not included in this compilation discusses the WCCC (Weak Cosmic Censorship Conjecture), and why it holds, as well as the scales where spacetime is non-commutative.

² Standing in for Quantum Physics in general.

4. Papers, comments and discussions

The compilation from [5] can be found in Appendix A. Of course later updates and newer papers or revisions are at [8].

5. Conclusions

We expect periodic publications of such status paper. The next one is planned in 2025.

We hope this helps people track our work in a concise and offline manner.

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Appendix A

See [8] for the latest.

The PDF is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13345964>, and the HTML is the present site [8].

A full copy can also be [obtained on this site](#).